

CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDY OF THE REACTION BETWEEN ALUMINIUM NITRATE AND ALKALI

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Reactions between aluminium nitrate and alkalis (NaOH, NH₄OH) have been studied conductometrically. Different results have been obtained regarding composition of compounds formed, which appears to depend upon the prevailing pH, ionic concentration, and ageing. By suitable choice of conditions pure Na₂HAlO₂, Al(OH)₃, and nearly pure NaAlO₂ may be formed. Freshly precipitated Al(OH)₃ may also be quantitatively converted into AlCl₃, during titration with HCl.

The earlier conductometric work on the reactions between aluminium salts and alkalis has been summarised by Britton ("Conductometric Analysis", p. 139, Chapman & Hall, London, 1934).

Kolthoff (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1920, 112, 172) and Britton (*loc. cit.*) used aluminium sulphate and NaOH. Kolthoff carried out conductometric titrations both under increasing and decreasing pH and found the latter more helpful for precipitation of pure Al(OH)₃ provided that the temperature was not low. Britton obtained a number of breaks when the pH was increasing (0.003125*M* sulphate, 0.20*M*-NaOH), which they ascribed to basic salts and NaAlO₂, but no break agreed with pure Al(OH)₃.

The nitrate has to be preferred since NO₃⁻ is less prone to complex formation or adsorption. The results with NaOH deserve to be compared with those obtained with NH₄OH. Back-titration of salt-alkali mixtures with mineral acids may throw additional light on the reactions. These titrations were therefore undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

An accuracy better than 1% was easily assured by using a precision bridge, a valve oscillator, and a cell with inaccessible electrodes. The titrations were performed with alkali in the cell (decreasing pH) and the reverse. The results are shown in Table I and the titration graphs bearing the same numbers in Figs. 1-4.

TABLE I

No.	Cell.	Burette.	Inflection.		Remarks.
			Required for.	Found.	
1a	2 c.c. of 0.480 <i>N</i> Al nitrate + 18 c.c. water	0.505 <i>N</i> -NaOH	i. Al(OH) ₃ = 1.90 ii. NaAlO ₂ = 2.53	B. 1.75 C. 2.45	30°. Colloidal ppt. from 0.4 c.c.; heavy gelatinous ppt. from 1.9 c.c. and dissolving from 2.6 c.c.
1b	Do	Do	Do	i. 1.80 ii. 2.45	28°. Mixture heated to 80° after every addn. of alkali, then cooled.
1c	2 c.c. of 0.5155 <i>N</i> salt + 148 c.c. water	0.505 <i>N</i> -NaOH	i. Al(OH) ₃ = 2.04 ii. NaAlO ₂ = 2.72	i. 2.00 ii. 2.55	Bath temp. = 30°.
2a	1 c.c. of 1.01 <i>N</i> -NaOH + 19 c.c. water	0.480 <i>N</i> salt	i. NaAlO ₂ = 1.575 ii. Al(OH) ₃ = 2.10	i. 1.50 ii. 2.20	29°. Ppt. from 1.6, redissolved from 2.3. Extrapolated value for (ii) = 2.1.
2b	Do	Do	Do	i. 1.50 ii. 2.10	28°. Mixture heated as in 1b.
2c	1 c.c. of 1.01 <i>N</i> -NaOH + 149 c.c. water	0.5155 <i>N</i> salt	i. NaAlO ₂ = 1.469 ii. Al(OH) ₃ = 1.96	i. 1.40 ii. 1.96	Bath temp. = 30°.
3a	10 c.c. of 0.048 <i>N</i> salt + 45 c.c. of 0.093 <i>N</i> -NaOH	1 <i>N</i> -HCl	i. NaOH left = 3.73 ii. AlCl ₃ = 4.18	i. 3.40 ii. 4.20	30°. Ppt. from 3.6 c.c., redissolved from 4.0 c.c. Al(OH) ₃ stage would consume 0.48 c.c. of <i>N</i> -NaOH against 0.785 c.c. consumed at (i).
3b	40 c.c. of 0.024 <i>N</i> salt + 40 c.c. of 0.093 <i>N</i> -NaOH	Do	i. NaOH left = 2.76 ii. AlCl ₃ = 3.72	i. 2.25 ii. 3.45	31.5°. Al(OH) ₃ stage would consume 0.96 c.c. <i>N</i> -NaOH against found 1.47. Alkali retained at (ii) = 0.27 against required nil. Ppt. from 2.5 c.c.; redissolved from 3.0 c.c. acid.
3c	20 c.c. of 0.048 <i>N</i> salt + 40 c.c. of 0.093 <i>N</i> -NaOH	Do	Do	Do	32° Do

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TABLE I (contd.)

No.	Cell.	Burette.	Inflection. Required for.	Found.	Remarks.
4a	5c.c. of 0.48N salt+2c.c. water	0.978N-NH ₄ OH	Al(OH) ₃ = 2.45	2.55	30°. Colloidal ppt. from 24. Gelatinous ppt. from 25.
4b	5c.c. of 0.48 N salt+2c.c. of N-NH ₄ Cl+18c.c. water	Do	Do	Do	Do
4c	Salt same + 20c.c. 0.1N-KCl	Do	Do	Do	Do
5	1c.c. of 0.978 N NH ₄ OH+19c.c. water	0.48N salt	Al(OH) ₃ = 2.04	1.95	31°. Ppt. from 0.5c.c.; redissolved from 2.0c.c.

DISCUSSION

Titration of Al(NO₃)₃ with NaOH.—In the titration (1a) the first break B occurs at 1.75 c.c. of NaOH (2.763 equiv. per mole salt). Since the mobilities of $\frac{1}{3}\text{Al}^{3+}$ and Na^+ are practically equal (about 41 at 18°) the slope of AB is small. B corresponds to $12\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3 \cdot \text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, but it is safer to consider it to be an adsorption compound as there is a fine colloidal precipitate from the commencement.

FIG. 1

Titration of Al(NO₃)₃ with NaOH.

FIG. 2

Titration of NaOH with Al(NO₃)₃.

Another break occurred at C=3.87 equiv. (required 4.0 equiv. for NaAlO_2). It appears that about 3% of the precipitate formed at first is rendered insoluble due to ageing. This is supported by a turbidity, which persists even at D (excess alkali).

in the titration (1b) the mixture was heated to 80° after every addition of alkali and then cooled to thermostat temperature. The break corresponding to B was then much sharper, perhaps due to reduced adsorption. The second inflection maintained its location.

With more dilute salt solution (1c) the discrepancy in B was reduced to 2%, but that in C was increased to over 6% and the residual turbidity was more pronounced. It appears that reduction in ionic concentration may increase the ageing effect.

Titration of NaOH with Al(NO₃)₃.—When the titrations were reversed, the usual precipitation of Al(OH)₃ appeared momentarily and soon disappeared in the excess alkali. There could be no question of ageing, and we expected the first break at 1.575 c.c. for NaAlO₂ in (2a), but found it only at 1.50 c.c. salt, F. Subsequently, there were indefinite breaks (FGHJ), the last one (J) at 2.20 c.c. against 2.17 c.c. expected for Al(OH)₃. This situation leaves the possibility for the following reactions open:—

Precipitation occurs just before G so that the subsequent portion of the graph may be vitiated by adsorption of Al³⁺. It is not surprising that the extrapolations of FG and KJ produce an intersection at 2.10 c.c., the value expected for pure Al(OH)₃. Prasad, Mehta, and Joshi (this *Journal*, 1930, 7, 973) from their own work pointed out the possibility of formation of Na₂HAIO₃ and Na₃AlO₃, the minimum conductivity corresponding to (iii); but this work was not corroborated by that of Britton (*loc. cit.*, p. 141).

FIG. 3

This titration was repeated, as stated in (2b). The mixture was heated, as stated in (1b). The first inflection maintained its location, indicating thereby that the salts formed were stable enough not to be affected by heating. The points on the intermediate branch (FGHJ) now fell on a smoother graph and led to the correct value for Al(OH)₃ automatically, perhaps indicating decreased adsorption. Similar results were produced when one started with a more dilute solution of alkali (2c).

Back-titration of Excess Alkali.—In a number of titrations we started with salt in the cell to which a known excess of NaOH had been added. This ensured the formation of salts like NaAlO₂. The excess alkali was then titrated back with 1N-HCl (3a, 3b, 3c). In (3a) the first inflection is at 4.90 equivs. against 5.0 required (NaOH bound) for the reaction (a).

Here the alkali : salt ratio was 1:25 at the commencement. When this ratio was reduced to 1:12 in 3b, 3c, the bound alkali dropped to 4.6 equivs. There is therefore no possibility of

obtaining pure Na_2HAlO_3 by mixing equivalent quantities of the salt and NaOH . These experiments perhaps indicate that Na_2HAlO_3 is quite a stable salt.

A second inflection occurred at 0, 0.843, 0.843 equiv. NaOH bound respectively in 3a, 3b, 3c. We may conclude that whole of the aluminium taken was converted into AlCl_3 in 3a, but this stage was not attained in 3b and 3c. It would be curious if the reaction (b) is involved.

One may note that the concentration of Al^{3+} in 3b and 3c was almost double of that in 3a.

FIG. 4

Titration with Ammonia and the Reverse.—The graphs are shown in Fig. 4. The titrations were satisfactory in neither direction for analytical purposes. The ammonia consumed was always 4% higher than that required for the complete precipitation of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$. The precipitation of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ is complete only when the pH is about 7 (Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", p. 410, Longmans, Green, 1951), which implies that a slight excess of ammonia must be present. The end point was not affected by the addition of ammonium or potassium chloride in small quantities.

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